

Additional information 1: The (incomplete) nucleotide sequence of the beet-infecting TuYV isolate obtained via Illumina sequencing. Ambiguous nucleotides (N) at the 5' and 3' end are added based on a TuYV alignment of GenBank isolates.

```
NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNTGCAATTTGTTGCTCACGATAACTTTC
ACACTTTAGAAAGTCAGGAAAGTCAGATACCTCCACCCAAAGCAAGTAACGTTTCTTCTAGC
AGGTCTATTGCTTAACATTAACAATTTGTCAAAGCAATCAAAGAGCGCAACAATGAATTC
AAAAC TGATATTTTCTTCGCTCTCTGCTCTATCAGCTTCCTCTCCACCTCGGAGACCACAT
CCACGATGATGTCAGGAAGTCCATACTTGCCCTGAACCAGAGCTTTGTGCCTGGTTCTCT
TTACAAACGGGATATGCTCCCGCCTCCACCTCAGGCCGTGTTAACTTATACGTGCCAGGAA
CCAAGACCTCTCGCGGAAGAATCATAACAACGATCTTTTTCGCGAGCGATTTCTCAGAAAAGCT
CAAGAGATTTCCAGAATGCCTATTCGGTAGCCTTGAGTATTTCCAGCGATTTCTATCAACAT
GGACTAAAGACGTTGAAAGACGTATCTTTTCTCGCTGTTCGAGAAATTCCTCTGGGGTCTGA
CACGCTTGTGGAGCTACTAATCTTGGCGAGCTTCTCCGCGTTATGGTGGTTGGTGAGCAA
TTTCACAAC TCCCGTCTTCTGTCTCGCCTTGCTGTACACTGTTACAAGATTTATGGTGAAGA
TGGTTTCATTTCTTTTTGGAGGATTGCCAATCTGGATCATTTTCGATTGCTTTCTACTCCTGA
AGAAATCCTTTTCAGCTCTTCGGTCTACACCGAAATGTTTGTATGAAAAGGCTATAGACGGT
TTCAAGAGTTTCACTATCCCACAGAGCCCCCAAATCTTGCGTGATTCCCATCACCCACG
CAAGCGGAAACCACGCTGGCTACGCCAGCTGTGTCAAGCTATAACAACGGCGAAAACGCTT
TAATGACGGCAACCCACGTTCTACGTGACTGCCCAATGCTGTAGCTATTTCCGCCAAAGG
GCTTAAAAC TCGGATTCCTACTCGCTGAATTCAAACAATTGCGAAATCCGACAAAGGTGAT
GTTACCCTCCTCCGCGGCCCCCCCCACCTGGGAAGGACTGTGCGGCTGCAAAGCGGCCAAC
GTCATTACAGCCGCCACCCTAGCAAAC TGC AAAGCATCCATATACTCTTTTGAGAGAGATG
GCTGGGTTAGCGGTTATGCCGAGATTGTGGGCTCAGAAGGTACCGATGTTATGGTCCTGAG
CCACACGGAAGGAGGACACTCCGGAAGCCCCTACTTTAATGGTAAAACCATTTTAGGGGTT
CATTCAGGTGCCAGTGCTACAGGAAATTACAAC TTGATGGCACCAATCCCGCCCCTCCCCG
GACTCACAAGTCCGACTTATGTGTTTGA AACACCGCACCAAGGAAGAGTTTTCGCAC
AAGAAGATATCGCCGAGATCGAAAGATCTCTATGCGCAAGCAGTAGAGAGATCGAATCGA
ACGAAAAATTTCAAGTCTAAGACTGGAACAAATTGGGCTGATATGGAGGATGATGAAGAC
ATCTTCTTCGAAAGCAGAGAAGATCTGTTCGGGAAACGGAGTGCGCGGCGCCGACCGCGA
AACAAACGGAGAAGGCAGCTTCACCCCAAAGACAAACAACGTCGATGGAAAAGAGATGA
TGGAGAAAATAATCTCATCTCTGGTGGGGAAGATAAATCTCGGGAACATCGAGAAGAAAG
TGATAGAGGAGATCTCCGCGAAAGCGATGAAAGCTCCAAAATCCCGCCGAGAAGAGCCC
CAAAGAAACAGCCGGAGAGTTCGAAAGATACTTCTCCTCGCTCTACAGCTGGGAAATACC
```

AACCTCCCCACGTGAGGTCCCCGGCTTCCGTCACTGCGGTAAGCTGCCCAATACTACCAC
CCCAAGCAAAAAGAAGAATCCAGCTGGGGGAAAACCCTCGTCGGGAACCATCCCGCGTT
GGGTGAAAAGACAAGCGGCTTCGGCTGGCCCAAGTTCGGCCCCGAAGCGGAACTGAAGA
GCCTGCGACTGCAGGCTTCACGGTGGCTGGAACGCGCCCAGTCCGCAGAAATACCCTCTG
ACGCTGAGAGGGAGCGTGTGATTCAAAGACCGCAGATGTTTACCATCCTTGCCAAACAA
ATGGACCTGCGGCAACCCGAGGAGGAGCACTGACCTGGAACAACCTTCATGATTGATTTC
AACAGGCGGTGTTCTCGCTGGAGTTCGATGCCGGAATCGGCGTCCCCTATATTGCCTATGG
CAAGCCCACACACCGTGGGTGGGTAGAAGATCAGACACTCCTTCCGGTCCTAGCTCAATT
GACCTTCATCCGACTACAGAAGATGTTGGAGGTTAGTTTCGAAGATATGGGACCAGAGGA
ACTGATCCAGAACGGTTTTGTGCGACCCCATCCGATTATTCGTGAAAGGGGAGCCCCACAA
ACAAGCGAAGCTCGATGAAGGCCGCTACCGCCTCATTATGAGCGTTTTCCCTCGTGGATCAA
TTGGTGGCCCGGGTTCTGTTCCAAAACCAGAACAAAGCGGGAAATTGCCCTGTGGAGGGCC
ATCCCCAGTAAACCCGGTTTTGGCTTGTCCACGGACGAGCAAGTGCTGGACTTTGTGAAA
GGTTTGGCCCGTCAAGTAGGCACTACGACAACAGAGGTAGTTGCCAATTGGAAAAATTAC
TTGACGCCACGGATTGCTCCGGTTTTGACTGGAGTGTTGCGGACTGGATGCTTACGATG
ATATGATCGTCCGCAATAGACTTACCATCGACCTCAACCCTGTTACAGAAAGATTAAGATCC
TGTTGGTTGAGGTGTGTTTTCAAACCTCAGTGCTATGCCTGAGTGATGGTACCCTTTTAGCCCA
AACCATCCGGGCGTTTCAGAAAAGTGGGAGCTACAATACTTCAAGCTCCAACCTCCCGGAT
CAGAGTTATGGCCGCCTTTCATACAGGTGCTGCCTGGGCTATGGCGATGGGCGATGACGCC
CTCGAGTCCAATCCCGCTGACCTAGCAGCGTACAAAAGACTAGGTTTTCAAGGTTGAGGTTT
CCGGACAACCTGGAATTCTGCTCTCACATATTTAGAGCGCCGGACCTCGCCCTCCCTGTGAA
TGAAAATAAAATGATCTACAAACTGATCTATGGCTACAATCCAGGGAGCGGAAACGCTGAG
GTAGTTTCAAACACTTAGCCGCTTGTTTCTCAGTTCTGAACGAGTTGCGGCACGATCCAG
CGTCCGTTGAACTTCTTTACTCGTGGTTAGTCGACCCGGTGCTACCACAAAAGATACCAGG
AGAGTAAAGAAGAGAAGAAGTTAGCCCTACATACGTAAGTTGCAAGTAAGGGAAACAAA
GTCTTACACCCGAGTATAAACATAGATTACAAGTTCCTAGCAGGCTTTTCCGCAGGCTTCTT
GTAAAGCATAACCAGTTTCGACACTCGGATTATACATAATCTACCTGAGAATTTCAACCCACC
TGAGATCAATCGTTAATGAATACGGTCGTGGGTAGAAGAACAATCAATGGAAGAAGACGA
CCACGGAGGCAAACACGACGCGCTCAGCGCTCTCAGCCAGTGGTTGTGGTCCAAGCCTCT
CGGACAACACAACGCCGACCAAGACGACGACGAAGAGGCGGTAACCGGACAGGAAGAA
CTGTTCCCTACCAGAGGAGCAGGTTTCGAGCGAGACATTTGTTTTCTCAAAGACAATCTCGC
GGGAAGTTCCAGCGGAGCAATCACGTTCCGGCCGAGTCTATCAGACTGCCAGCATTCTCT
AATGGAATGCTCAAGGCCTACCATGAGTATAAAATCTCAATGGTCATTTTGGAGTTCATCTC
CGAAGCCTCTTCCAAAACCTCCGGTTCATCGTTACGAGCTGGACCCACACTGTAAACTC
AACTCCCTTTCTCAACTATCAACAAATTCGGGATCACAAAGCCCGGGAGGAGGGCGTTTA
CAGCGTCTTACATCAACGGGACAGAATGGCACGACGTTGCCGAGGACCAATTCAGGATCC
TCTACAAAGGCAATGGTTCTTCATCGATAGCTGGTTCTTTCAGAATCACCATAAAGTGCCAA

TTCCACAATCCCAAATAGGTAGACGAGGAACCCGGCCCCAGCCCAGGGCCTTCTCCCTCTC
CACAACCCACACCCCAAAAGAAATATCGTTTTATCGTCTACACTGGAGTCCCCGTGACCCG
TATAATGGCTCAATCCACAGATGACGCCATCTCTTTGTACGACATGCCTTCCCAAAGGTTTC
GCTACATAGAGGACGAGAACATGAACTGGACGAACCTCGATTCCCGATGGTATTCCCAGAA
TTCTTTGAAAGCCATCCCGATGATAATAGTACCAGTCCCTCAAGGTGAGTGGACAGTGGAA
ATTTTCGATGGAGGGGTATCAACCAACCTCAAGTACCACAGATCCTAATAAGGACAAACAAG
ATGGTCTTATTGCATACAATGATGACCTCAAGGAGGGTTGGAATGTTGGGGTTTATAATAAT
GTGGAGATAACCAACAATAAGGCCGACAACACTCTCAAGTACGGCCACCCAGACATGGAA
CTCAATAGCTGTCATTTCAATCAAGGACAGTGTCTGGAAAGAGACGGAGATTTGACTTGTC
ACATCAAAAACAACCTGGTGATGACGCCTCCTTCTTTATTGTTGGACCCGCTGTTTCAGAAGCA
ATCAAAGTACAATTACGCCGGTTCATACGGAGCTTGGACAGATCGGATGATGGAGATAGGA
TTGATAGCCATAGCACTTGATGAACAAGGCTCATCCGGTTCAAAAAGACAGAAAGACCA
AAGAGAGTTGGGCACTCCATGGCAGTCTCAACCTGGGAGACTATAAACTTACCGGAGAAG
GAAAACCTCCGAGAAAATCGAAACCAGTCAAAGACAAGACTTTAAAACCTAACCTAAACA
AGGTTTCTCAGATGCTGGTTCTGAAGACAACAAGGAATGGGATTTACACCCGGGACTCG
AATGTTTCTTCTGAAGACTTCGAGGAACCCCGTGAGGTTTCAGAATGACGATCTCCTCAGA
GATAGAGGAATTGTAGTAGATCCCTCCTTGTGGAAATACCTGACTCACCTCCTCCGAGAG
CGGACCATAAGGACACAGATCCTTGGGCTGAGGTTGAAAGATATAAATCTTCCCATAAAGC
CCTTGTCGGCGAGGACACGCGTTCGACAAATCATCCTTGACAGGAGGTTGCTTGCTGGC
GGCAGCCTTAGAAAGCTGAAGCCGGTTACACCGGACGAGTATGAGCAGGCAAAACTGAA
AGATGAGTCGAGACTCCAGTATGAACAGGATCTCGCTGACTATCACAAGACAATGAAAAG
ACCCGGAAGCGGTTAATACCACGTGATGACGGTGAGCTCATGGAGATGGATCCTTCTCAA
CGTAAATTGATGAAGAACGCTGGAGTCAACCTTGATAAGTATGGTAGACCAGTTAGAAAAG
GTTTCCTCTCTTTCAGGAAATAGTCCCCAGTACTTAACTGGCTCGTTGGTAGTGATACGAG
GCGAAAATCAAACTACCCTTATCTAGCTTTATTTCTATTTAGCTAATAAAGTCAAGCCAGA
GACATTAACCTGGAACGACTCCGTTTTGCGGATAGGCAACGAGTGTTTTACGCNNNNNNN
NNNNNNNNNNNNNN

Additional information 2: The nucleotide sequence of the combined regions 2, 3 and 4 of TuYV isolate 5470. The overlapping parts with the adjacent TuYV regions, needed for Gibson Assembly, are highlighted in grey.

```
AAGCTATACAACGGCGAAAACGCTTTAATGACGGCAACTCACGTTCTACGTGACTGCCCCA
ATGCTGTAGCTATTTCCGCCAAAGGGCTTAAGACTCGGATTCCACTCGCTGAATTTAAAAC
AATTGCGAAATCCGACAAAGGTGATGTTACCCTTCTCCGCGGCCCCCCCCAACTGGGAAGG
ACTGTTAGGCTGCAAAGCGGCCAACGTCATTACAGCCGCCAACCTAGCAAATGCAAAGC
ATCCATATACTCTTTTGAGAGAGATGGCTGGGTTAGCGGTTATGCCGAGATTGTGGGTTCAG
AAGGTACCGATGTTATGGTCCTGAGCCACACGGAAGGGGGACACTCCGGAAGCCCCTACT
TCAATGGTAAAACCATCTTAGGGGTTCAATCAGGTGCCAGTGCTACAGGAAATTACAATT
GATGGCACCAATCCCGCCCCTCCCCGGACTCACAAGTCCGACTTATGTGTTTGAAACCACC
GCACCACAAGGAAGAGTTTTTCGCACAAGAAGATATCGCCGAGATTGAAGATCTCTATGCGC
AAGCAGTAGAGAGATCGAATCGAACGAAAAATTTCAAGTCTAAGACTGGAACAAATTGGG
CTGATATGGAGGATGATGAAGACATCTTCTTCGAAAGCAGAGAAGATCTGTGCGGAAACG
GAGTGCGCGGCGCCGACCGCGAAACAAACGGAGAAGGCAGCTCCACCCCAAAGACAAA
CAACGTCGATGGGAAAGAGATGATGGAGAAAATAATCTCATCTCTGGTGGGGAAAATAAAT
CTCGAGAACATCGAGAAGAAAGTGATAGAGGAGATATCCGCGAAAGCGTTGAAAGCTCCA
AAGTCCC GCCGAGAAGAGCCCCAAAGAAACAGCCGGAGAGTTCGAAAGATACTTCTCC
TCGCTCTACA ACTGGGAGGTACCAGCCTCCCCACGTGAGGTCCCCGGCTTCCGTC ACTGCG
GCAAGCTGCCCCAATACTACCACCCCAAGCAAAAAGAAGAATCCAGCTGGGGGAAAACC
CTCGTCGGGAACCATCCCGCGTTGGGTGAAAAGACAAGCGGCTTCGGCTGGCCCAAGTTC
GGCCCCGAAGCAGAACTGAAGAGCCTGCGACTGCAGGCTTCACGGTGGCTGGAACGCGC
CCAGTCCGCAGAAATACCCTCTGACGCTGAGAGGGAGCGTGTGATTCAAAGACCGCAGA
TGTTTACCATCCTTGCCAAACAAATGGACCTGCGGCAACCCGAGGAGGAGCACTGACCTG
GAACA ACTTCATGATTGATTTCAAACAGGCGGTGTTCTCGCTGGAGTTCGATGCCGGAATC
GGCGTCCCCTATATTGCCTATGGCAAGCCCACACACCGTGGGTGGGTAGAAGATCAGACAC
TCCTTCCGGT CCTAGCTCAATTGACCTTCATCCGACTACAGAAGATGTTGGAGGTTAGTTTC
GAAGATATGGGACCAGAGGAGCTGATCCAGAACGGTTTGTGCGACCCCATCCGATTATTCC
TGAAAGGGGAGCCCCACAAACAAGCGAAGCTCGATGAAGGCCGCTACCGCCTCATTATGA
GCGTTTCCCTCGTGGATCAATTGGTGGCCCGGTTCTGTTCCAAAACCAGAACAAGCGGG
AAATTGCCCTGTGGAGGGCCATCCCCAGTAAACCCGGTTTTGGCTTGTCCACGGACGAGC
AAGTGCTGGACTTTGTGAAAGGTTTGGCCCGTCAAGTAGGCACTACGACAACAGAGGTAG
TTGCCAATTGGAAAATTACTTGACGCCACGGATTGCTCCGGTTTTGACTGGAGTGTTGC
```

GGACTGGATGCTTCACGATGATATGATCGTCCGCAATAGACTTACCATCGACCTCAACCCTG
TTACAGAAAGATTAAGATCCTGTTGGTTGAGGTGTGTTTCAAACCTCAGTGCTATGCCTGAG
TGATGGTACCCTTTTAGCCCAAACCCATCCGGGCGTTTCAGAAAAGTGGGAGCTACAATACT
TCAAGCTCCAACCTCCCGGATCAGAGTTATGGCCGCCTTTCATACAGGTGCTGCCTGGGCTA
TGGCGATGGGCGATGACGCCCTCGAGTCCAATCCCGCTGACCTAGCAGCGTACAAAAGAC
TAGGTTTCAAGGTTGAGGTTTCCGGACAACCTGGAATTCTGCTCTCACATATTTAGAGCGCC
GGACCTCGCCCTCCCTGTGAATGAAAATAAAATGATCTACAAACTGATCTATGGCTACAATC
CAGGGAGCGGAAACGCTGAGGTAGTTTCAAACCTACTTAGCCGCTTGTTTCTCAGTTCTGAA
CGAGTTGCGGCACGATCCAGCGTCCGTTGAACTTCTTTACTCGTGGTTAGTCGACCCGGTG
CTACCACAAAAGATACCAGGAGAGTAAAGAAGAGAAGAAGTTAGCCCTACATACGTAAGT
TGCAAGTAAGGGAAACAAAGTCTTACACCCGAGTATAAACATAGATTACAAGTTCCTAGCA
GGCTTTTCCGCAGGCTTCTTGTTAAGCATAACAGTTTCGACACTCGGATTATACATAATCTA
CCTGAGAATTTCAACCCACCTGAGATCAATCGTTAATGAATACGGTCGTGGGTAGGAGAAC
AATCAATGGAAGAAGACGACCACGGAGGCAAACACGACGCGCTCAGCGGTCTCAGCCAG
TGGTTGTGGTCCAAACCTCTCGGGCAACACAACGCCGACCTAGACGACGACGAAGAGGTA
ATAACCGGACAAGAGGAACTGTTCCCTACCAGAGGAGCAGGCTCAAGCGAGACATTTGTTT
TCTCAAAGACAATCTCGCGGGAAGTTCCAGCGGAGCAATCACGTTCCGGCCGAGTCTAT
CAGACTGCCCAGCATTCTCTAATGGAATACTCAAGGCCTACCATGAGTATAAAATCTCGATG
GTCATTTTGGAGTTCGTCTCCGAAGCCTCTTCCCAAACCTCCGGTCCATCGCTTACGAGC
TGGACCCACACTGTAAACTCAACTCCCTTTCCCTCAACTATCAACAAGTTCGGGATCACAAA
GCCCGGAAAGCGGCGTTTACAGCGTCTTACATCAACGGGAAGGAATGGCACGACGTTGC
CGAGGACCAATTCAGGATCCTCTACAAAGGCAATGGTTCTTCATCGATAGCTGGTTCTTTCA
GAATCACCATAAAGTGCCAATTCACAATCCCAAATAGGTAGACGAGGAACCCGGCCCCA
GCCAGGGCCTTCTCCCTCTCCACAACCCACACCCCAAAGAAATATCGTTTTATCGTCTA
CACCGGAGTCCCGTGACCCGTATAATGGCTCAATCCACAGATGACGCCATCTCTTTGTAC
GACATGCCTTCCCAAAGGTTTCGCTACATAGAGGACGAGAACATGAA

Additional information 3: The nucleotide sequence of the two Gblocks used for completing the TuYV genome based on the Illumina sequence. The overlapping parts with the adjacent TuYV regions, needed for Gibson Assembly, are highlighted in grey. The underlined sequence is based on an alignment of NCBI TuYV isolates. Highlighted in black is the sequence complementary to the pDIVA plasmid, needed for Gibson Assembly.

TAAGGAAGTTCATTTCAATTTGGAGAGGACAAAAGAAACCAGGAGGGAATCCTAAGTTGAT
GCAATTTGTTGCTCACGATAACTTTCACACTTTAGAAAGTCAGGAAAGTCAGATACCTCCAC
CCAAAGCAAGTAACGTTTCTTCTAGCAGGTCTATTGCTTAACATTAACAATTTGTCAAAGC
AATCAAAGAGCGCAACAATGAATTCAAACACTGATATTTTTCTTCGCTCTCTGCTCTATCAGC
TTCCTCTCCACCTCGGAGACCACATCCACGATGATGTCAGGAAGTCCATACTTGCCCCTGA
ACCAGAGCTTTGTGCCTGGTTCTCTTTACAAACGGGATATGCTCCCGCCTCCACCTCAGGC
CGTGTTAACTTATACGTGCCAGGAACCAAGACCTCTCGCGGAAGAATCATAACAACGATCTT
TTGCGAGCGATTTCTCAGAAAAGCTCAAGAGATTTCCAGAATGCCTATTCGGTAGCCTTGA
GTATTTCCAGCGATTTCTATCAACATGGACTAAAGACGTTGAAAGACGTATCTTTTCTCGCT
GTCGAGAAATCCTCTGGGGTCTGACACGCTTGTGGAGCTCACTAATCTTGGCGAGCTTCT
CCGCGTTATGGTGGTTGGTGAGCAATTTCAAACTCCCGTCTTCTGTCTCGCCTTGCTGTAC
ACTGTTACAAGATTTATGGTGAAGATGGTTTCATTTCTTTTTGGAGGATTGCCAATCTGGAT
CATTTGATTGCTTTCTCACTCCTGAAGAAATCCTTTTCAGCTCTTCGGTCTACACCGAAAT
GTTTGTATGAAAAGGCTATAGACGGTTTCAAGAGTTTCACTATCCACAGAGCCCCCAA
ATCTTGCGTGATTCCCATCACCCACGCAAGCGGAAACCACGCTGGCTACGCCAGCTGTGTC
AAGCTATAACAACGGCGAAAACGCTTTA

TCGCTACATAGAGGACGAGAACATGAACTGGACGAACCTCGATTCCCGATGGTATTCCCAG
AATCTTTGAAAGCCATCCCGATGATAATAGTACCAGTCCCTCAAGGTGAGTGGACAGTGG
AAATTTGATGGAGGGGTATCAACCAACCTCAAGTACCACAGATCCTAATAAGGACAAACA
AGATGGTCTTATTGCATAACAATGATGACCTCAAGGAGGGTTGGAATGTTGGGGTTTATAATA
ATGTGGAGATAACCAACAATAAGGCCGACAACACTCTCAAGTACGGCCACCCAGACATGG
AACTCAATAGCTGTCATTTCAATCAAGGACAGTGTCTGGAAAGAGACGGAGATTTGACTTG
TCACATCAAACAACCTGGTGATGACGCCTCCTTCTTTATTGTTGGACCCGCTGTTTCAGAAG
CAATCAAAGTACAATTACGCCGGTTCATACGGAGCTTGGACAGATCGGATGATGGAGATAG

GATTGATAGCCATAGCACTTGATGAACAAGGCTCATCCGGTTCCAAAAAGACAGAAAGAC
CAAAGAGAGTTGGGCACTCCATGGCAGTCTCAACCTTGGAGACTATAAACTTACCGGAGA
AGGAAAACCTCCGAGAAAATCGAAACCAGTCAAAGACAAGACTTTAAAACCTCAACCTAAA
CAAGGTTTCTCAGATGCTGGTTCTGAAGACAACAAGGAATGGGATTTACACCCGGGACT
CGAATGTTTCTTCTGAAGACTTCGAGGAACCCCGTGAGGTTTCAAGATGACGATCTCCTCA
GAGATAGAGGAATTGTAGTAGATCCCTCCTTGTGGAAATACCTGACTCACCTCCTCCGAG
AGCGGACCATAAGGACACAGATCCTTGGGCTGAGGTTGAAAGATATAAATCTTCCCATAAA
GCCCTTGTCCGCGAGGACACGCGTTCCCGACAATCATCCTTGACAGGAGGTTGCTTGCTG
GCGGCAGCCTTAGAAAGCTGAAGCCGGTTACACCGGACGAGTATGAGCAGGCAAAACTG
AAAGATGAGTCGAGACTCCAGTATGAACAGGATCTCGCTGACTATCACAAAGACAATGAAA
AGACCCGGAAGCGCGTTAATACCACGTGATGACGGTGAGCTCATGGAGATGGATCCTTCTC
AACGTAAATTGATGAAGAACGCTGGAGTCAACCTTGATAAGTATGGTAGACCAGTTAGAAA
AGGTTTCTCTCTTTCAGGAAATAGTCCCCAGTACTTAACTGGCTCGTTGGTAGTGATACG
AGGCGAAAATCAAAACTACCCTTATCTAGCTTTATTTCTATTTAGCTAATAAAGTCAAGCCA
GAGACATTAAACTGGAACGACTCCGTTTTGCGGATAGGCAACGAGTGTTTTACGCTGGGAT
AACTCCCTACGGCA**GGGTCGGCATGGCATCTCCACCTCCTC**

Additional information 4: The nucleotide sequence of the TuYV insert in a pDIVA vector in *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*. Highlighted in black is the sequence complementary to the pDIVA plasmid, needed for Gibson Assembly.

TAAGGAAGTTCATTTCAATTTGGAGAGGACAAAAGAAACCAGGAGGGAATCCTAAGTTGAT
GCAATTTGTTGCTCACGATAACTTTCACACTTTAGAAGTCAGGAAAGTCAGATACCTCCAC
CCAAAGCAAGTAACGTTTCTTCTAGCAGGTCTATTGCTTAACATTAACAATTTGTCAAAGC
AATCAAAGAGCGCAACAATGAATTCAAAACTGATATTTTTCTTCGCTCTCTGCTCTATCAGC
TTCTCTCCACCTCGGAGACCACATCCACGATGATGTCAGGAAGTCCATACTTGCCCCTGA
ACCAGAGCTTTGTGCCTGGTTCTCTTTACAAACGGGATATGCTCCCGCCTCCACCTCAGGC
CGTGTTAACTTATACGTGCCAGGAACCAAGACCTCTCGCGGAAGAATCATACAACGATCTT
TTGCGAGCGATTTCTCAGAAAAGCTCAAGAGATTTCCAGAATGCCTATTCGGTAGCCTTGA
GTATTTCCAGCGATTTCTATCAACATGGACTAAAGACGTTGAAAGACGTATCTTTTCTCGCT
GTCGAGAAATCCTCTGGGGTCTGACACGCTTGTGGAGCTCACTAATCTTGGCGAGCTTCT
CCGCGTTATGGTGGTTGGTGAGCAATTTCAAACTCCCGTCTTCTGTCTCGCCTTGCTGTAC
ACTGTTACAAGATTTATGGTGAAGATGGTTTCATTTCTTTTTGGAGGATTGCCAATCTGGAT
CATTCGATTGCTTTCTCACTCCTGAAGAAATCCTTTTCAGCTCTTCGGTCTACACCGAAAT
GTTTGTATGAAAAGGCTATAGACGGTTTCAAGAGTTTCACTATCCCACAGAGCCCCCAAA

ATCTTGCGTGATTCCCATCACCCACGCAAGCGGAAACCACGCTGGCTACGCCAGCTGTGTC
AAGCTATAACAACGGCGAAAACGCTTTAATGACGGCAACTCACGTTCTACGTGACTGCCCCA
ATGCTGTAGCTATTTCCGCCAAAGGGCTTAAGACTCGGATTCCACTCGCTGAATTTAAAAC
AATTGCGAAATCCGACAAAGGTGATGTTACCCTTCTCCGCGGCCCCCCCCAACTGGGAAGG
ACTGTTAGGCTGCAAAGCGGCCAACGTCATTACAGCCGCCAACCTAGCAAATGCAAAGC
ATCCATATACTCTTTTGAGAGAGATGGCTGGGTTAGCGGTTATGCCGAGATTGTGGGTTTCAG
AAGGTACCGATGTTATGGTCCTGAGCCACACGGAAGGGGGACACTCCGGAAGCCCCTACT
TCAATGGTAAAACCATCTTAGGGGTTCAATCAGGTGCCAGTGCTACAGGAAATTACAATT
AATGGCACCAATCCCGCCCCTCCCCGGACTCACAAGTCCGACTTATGTGTTTGAAACCACC
GCACCACAAGGAAGAGTTTTTCGCACAAGAAGATATCGCCGAGATTGAAGATCTCTATGCGC
AAGCAGTAGAGAGATCGAATCGAACGAAAAATTTCAAGTCTAAGACTGGAACAAATTGGG
CTGATATGGAGGATGATGAAGACATCTTCTTCGAAAGCAGAGAAGATCTGTGCGGAAACG
GAGTGCGCGGCGCCGACCGCGAAACAAACGGAGAAGGCAGCTCCACCCCAAAGACAAA
CAACGTCGATGGGAAAGAGATGATGGAGAAAATAATCTCATCTCTGGTGGGGAAAATAAAT
CTCGAGAACATCGAGAAGAAAGTGATAGAGGAGATATCCGCGAAAGCGTTGAAAGCTCCA
AAGTCCCGCCGCAGAAGAGCCCCAAAGAAACAGCCGGAGAGTTCGAAAGATACTTCTCC
TCGCTCTACAAC TGGGAGGTACCAGCCTCCCCACGTGAGGTCCCCGGCTTCCGTCACTGCG
GCAAGCTGCCCAATACTACCACCCCAAGCAAAAAGAAGAATCCAGCTGGGGGAAAACC
CTCGTCGGGAACCATCCCGCGTTGGGTGAAAAGACAAGCGGCTTCGGCTGGCCCAAGTTC
GGCCCCGAAGCAGAACTGAAGAGCCTGCGACTGCAGGCTTACGGTGGCTGGAACGCGC
CCAGTCCGCAGAAATACCCTCTGACGCTGAGAGGGAGCGTGTGATTCAAAGACCGCAGA
TGTTTACCATCCTTGCCAAACAATGGACCTGCGGCAACCCGAGGAGGAACACTGACCTG
GAACAACCTTCATGATTGATTTCAAGCAGGCGGTGTTCTCGCTGGAGTTCGATGCCGGAATC
GGCGTCCCCTATATTGCCTATGGCAAGCCCACACACCGTGGGTGGGTAGAAGATCAGACAC
TCCTTCCAGTCTAGCTCAATTAACCTTCATCCGACTACAGAAGATGTTGGAGGTTAGTTTC
GAAGATATGGGACCAGGGGAGCTGATCCAGAACGGTTTGTGCGACCCCATCCGATTATTTG
TGAAAGGGGAGCCCCACAAACAAGCGAAGCTCGATGAAGGCCGCTACCGCCTCATTATGA
GCGTTTCCCTCGTGGATCAATTGGTGGCCCGGGTTCTGTTCCAAAACCAGAACAAAGCGGG
AAATTGCCCTGTGGAGGGCCATCCCCAGTAAACCCGGTTTTGGCTTGTCACGGACGAGC
AAGTGCTGGACTTTGTGAAAGGTTTTGGCCCGTCAAGTAGGCACTACGACAACAGAGGTAG
TTGCCAATTGGAAAAATTACTTGACGCCACGGATTGCTCCGGTTTTGACTGGAGTGTTGC
GGACTGGATGCTTCACGATGATATGATCGTCCGCAACAGACTTACCATCGACCTCAACCCT
GTTACAGAAAGATTAAGATCCTGTTGGTTGAGGTGTGTTTCAAACCTCAGTGCTATGCCTGA
GTGATGGTACCCTTTTAGCCCAAACCCATCCGGGCGTTCAGAAAAGTGGGAGCTACAATAC
TTCAAGCTCCAACCTCCCGGATCAGAGTTATGGCCGCCTTTCATACAGGTGCTGCCTGGGCT
ATGGCGATGGGCGATGACGCCCTCGAGTCCAATCCCGCTGACCTAGCAGCGTACAAAAGA
CTAGGTTTCAAGGTTGAGGTTTCCGGACAACCTGGAATTCTGCTCTCACATATTTAGAGCGC

CGGACCTCGCCCTCCCTGTGAACGAAAATAAGATGATCTACAACTGATCTATGGCTACAA
TCCAGGGAGCGGAAACGCTGAGGTAGTTTCAAACACTTAGCCGCTTGCTTCTCAGTTCTG
AACGAGTTGCGGCATGATCCAGCGTCCGTTGAACTTCTTTACTCGTGGTTAGTCGACCCGG
TGCTACCACAAAAGATACCAGGAGAGTAAAGAAGAGAAGAAGTTAGCCCTACATACGTAA
GTTGCAAGTAAGGGAAACAAAGTCTTACACCCGAGTATAAACATAGATTACAAGTTCCTAG
CAGGCTTTTCCGCAGGCTTCTTGTTAAGCATACCAGTTTCGACACTCGGATTATACATAATC
TACCTGAGAATTTCAACCCACCTGAGATCAATCGTTAACGAATACGGTCGTGGGTAGAAGA
ACAATCAATGGAAGAAGACGACCACGGAGGCAAGCACGACGCGCTCAGCGCTCTCAGCC
AGTGGTTGTGGTCCAAGCCTCTCGGACAACACAACGCCGACCAAGACGACGACGAAGAG
GCGGTAACCGGACAGGAAGAAGTGTTCCTACCAGAGGAGCAGGTTTCGAGCGAGACATTTG
TTTTCTCAAAGACAATCTCGCGGGAAGTTCCAGCGGAGCAATCACGTTTCGGGTCGAGTC
TATCAGACTGCCCGGCATTGCTAATGGAATGCTCAAGGCCTACCATGAGTATAAAATCTCA
ATGGTCATTTTGGAGTTCATCTCCGAAGCCTCTTCCCAAATTCGGTTCATCGCTTACGA
GCTGGACCCACACTGTAAACTCAACTCCCTTTCCTCAACTATCAACAAATTCGGGATCACA
AAGCCCGGAGGAGGGCGTTTACAGCGTCTTACATCAACGGGACAGAATGGCACGACGTT
GCCGAGGGCCAATTCAGGATCCTCTACAAAGGCAATGGTCCTTCATCGATAGCTGGTTCTT
TCAGAATCACCATAAAGTGCCAATTCCACAATCCCAAATAGGTAGACGAGGAACCCGGCCC
CAGCCCAGGGCCTTCTCCCTCTCCACAACCCACACCCCAAAGAAATATCGTTTTATCGTC
TACACCGGAGTCCCCGTGACCCGTATAATGGCTCAATCCACAGATGACGCCATCTCTTTGTA
CGACATGCCTTCCCAAAGGTTTCGCTACATAGAGGACGAGAACATGAACTGGACGAACCT
CGATTCCCGATGGTATTCCAGAATTTCTTGAAAGCCATCCCGATGATAATAGTACCAGTCC
CTCAAGGTGAGTGGACAGTGGAAATTCGATGGAGGGGTATCAACCAACCTCAAGTACCA
CAGATCCTAATAAGGACAAACAAGATGGTCTTATTGCATACAATGATGACCTCAAGGAGGG
TTGGAATGTTGGGGTTTATAATAATGTGGAGATAACCAACAATAAGGCCGACAACACTCTC
AAGTACGGCCACCCAGACATGGAACTCAATAGCTGTCATTTCAATCAAGGACAGTGTCTGG
AAAGAGACGGAGATTTGACTTGTACATCAAACAACCTGGTGTGACGCCTCCTTCTTTAT
TGTTGGACCCGCTGTTTCAGAAGCAATCAAAGTACAATTACGCCGGTTCATACGGAGCTTGG
ACAGATCGGATGATGGAGATAGGATTGATAGCCATAGCACTTGATGAACAAGGCTCATCCG
GTTCCAAAAAGACAGAAAGACCAAAGAGAGTTGGGCACTCCATGGCAGTCTCAACCTTG
GAGACTATAAACTTACCGGAGAAGGAAAACCTCCGAGAAAATCGAAACCAGTCAAAGACA
AGACTTTAAAACCTAACCTAAACAAGGTTTCTCAGATGCTGGTTCTGAAGACAACAAGGA
ATGGGATTTACACCCGGGACTCGAATGTTTCTTCCCTGAAGACTTCGAGGAACCCCGTGAG
GTTTCAGAATGACGATCTCCTCAGAGATAGAGGAATTGTAGTAGATCCCTCCTTGTTGGAAA
TACCTGACTCACCTCCTCCGAGAGCGGACCATAAGGACACAGATCCTTGGGCTGAGGTTG
AAAGATATAAATCTTCCATAAAGCCCTTGTCGGCGAGGACACGCGTTCCCGACAATCATC
CTTGACAGGAGGTTTCGCTTGCTGGCGGCAGCCTTAGAAAAGCTGAAGCCGGTTACACCGGA
CGAGTATGAGCAGGCAAACTGAAAGATGAGTCGAGACTCCAGTATGAACAGGATCTCGC

TGACTATCACAAGACAATGAAAAGACCCGGAAGCGCGTTAATACCACGTGATGACGGTGA
GTCATGGAGATGGATCCTTCTCAACGTAAATTGATGAAGAACGCTGGAGTCAACCTTGAT
AAGTATGGTAGACCAGTTAGAAAAGGTTTCCTCTCTTTCAGGAAATAGTCCCCAGTACTT
AACTGGCTCGTTGGTAGTGATACGAGGCGAAAATCAAACCTACCCTTATCTAGCTTTATTTC
TATTTAGCTAATAAAGTCAAGCCAGAGACATTAACTGGAACGACTCCGTTTTGCGGATAG
GCAACGAGTGTTTTACGCTGGGATAACTCCCTACGGCA**GGGTCGGCATGGCATCTCCACCT**
CCTC